

EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF ANTI-INFLAMMATORY THERAPY ON THE DEGREE OF INTESTINAL DYSBIOSIS IN PATIENTS WITH RHEUMATOID ARTHRITIS

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Abstract. *As a result of the conducted studies, it was found that patients with rheumatoid arthritis, deforming osteoarthritis, primary gout have disorders of the microflora of various biotopes. The most pronounced disorders were noted in the intestinal microflora — up to the development of dysbiosis of the II — III degree, which has certain characteristic features: with rheumatoid arthritis, there is a decrease in endogenous flora and an increase in facultative bacteria, with deforming osteoarthritis, the amount of endogenous flora is sharply reduced with a slight change in the facultative group of bacteria, with primary gout, the proportion of coliform bacteria increases. The inclusion of probiotics Bifidobacterium — PL and Lactobacterium in complex therapy of patients with rheumatoid arthritis, deforming osteoarthritis, primary gout leads to a good clinical and laboratory effect in 66.7% of treated patients, reducing the frequency and intensity of exacerbations of arthritis and, accordingly, improving the quality of life of patients.*

Key words: *rheumatoid arthritis, dysbiosis, inflammation, osteoarthritis, primary gout.*

Introduction. According to recent studies, the violation of normal flora, immune status and manifestations of the disease are considered as a unity, and in each case the role of the causal mechanism may belong to any of the components of this triad: dysbacteriosis, immune status and pathological process [2, 8]. Infectious factors play a role in the development of many rheumatic diseases, but their significance in different processes is not the same. In many rheumatic diseases, it is not possible to identify the "trigger factor", after which a number of immune and autoimmune reactions develop, determining the further course of the disease. Intestinal bacteria and their waste products can contribute to the development of arthritis, which affects various areas [1]. Some researchers believe that this type of bacteria may well participate in maintaining the barrier function of the intestinal wall, the disruption of which is indirectly associated with the development of rheumatoid arthritis [5, 7]. In this case, the permeability of the intestinal wall for microbial antigens and their toxins increases significantly, which is considered an important factor in the sensitization of the body to microbial antigens and, possibly, the development of autoimmune diseases, including arthritis [9].

Specifically, various microorganisms with a non-specific effect on the immune system may be associated with the development of arthritis, the disruption of which (in the presence of a genetic predisposition) determines the subsequent course of the disease [3, 4]. Currently, the issue of the participation of microorganisms in the pathogenesis of autoimmune inflammatory, degenerative and metabolic processes in the joints is being considered [6]. It is proposed to consider post-stress translocation of intestinal microflora as a mechanism of neuroimmune cooperation in the implementation of an adaptive response to the internal environment of the body. It is emphasized

that the effectiveness of the adaptive process depends on the state of the microbiocenosis as a mediating factor [10, 11].

Aim of the study: to study the state of automicroflora and the characteristics of the microbiocenosis of the colon in patients with rheumatoid arthritis (RA), deforming osteoarthritis (DOA) and primary gout (PG), to evaluate the effect of probiotic therapy on laboratory parameters and the clinical course of the disease.

Materials and methods. It is increasingly recognized that the study involved 150 patients aged 35-55 years with chronic inflammatory processes of the joints of non-infectious etiology: 70 RA, 40 DOA, 40 BP, of which 60 (20 from each group) included probiotics in the complex therapy. The patients underwent inpatient and outpatient treatment in the rheumatology department and clinic of TTA I. Patients with a confirmed diagnosis were selected for the study (randomized study). The control group consisted of 25 practically healthy individuals of the same sex and age who did not take anti-inflammatory, hormonal or antimicrobial drugs during the last two months before the study. All patients underwent comprehensive conventional treatment, including: vitamin therapy (oligovit, neurorubin, vitamin C, vitamin E, vitamins B1, B6, B12, etc.), non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (diclofenac, voltaren, ibuprofen, etc.), rehabilitation measures. According to the instructions, some patients were prescribed steroid anti-inflammatory drugs (prednisolone, etc.). Bifidumbacterium - PL and Lactobacterium - orom, produced in Uzbekistan, were used as biocorrectors. The drugs were prescribed 30 minutes before meals, in the morning and in the evening, 5 doses twice a day in courses of 14 days. The drugs were prescribed sequentially: a 14-day course of lactobacilli, then bifidobacteria - PL.

Table 1. The depth of dysbiotic diseases in patients with RA, DOA, PP (%)

Note: * - significance of differences: DK I-DK II, $p < 0.05$ 00- significance of differences: DK II-DK III, $p < 0.05$

Diagnosis	DK I		DK II		DK III	
	Π	%	Π	%	Π	%
RA= p=70, including	14	20,0 ±4,8	26	37,2±5,8*	0	42,8±5,9
— I degree/14	5	35,7±12,8	7	50,0±13,3	2	14,3±9,3 ° °
— II degree/35	7	20,0±6,7	10	28,6±7,6	8	51,4±8,4 ° °
— III degree/21	3	14,3± 7,6	6	28,6±9,8	2	57,1±10,8 ° °
DOA— p=40	9	22,5±6,6	14	35,0±7,5	7	42,5±7,8
BP— p=40	11	27,5±7,0	13	32,5 ±7,4	6	40,0±7,7

The following methods were used in the work: clinical and anamnestic examination and dynamic observation in the process of treating patients with chronic joint diseases: RA, DOA, BP. Laboratory examination to clarify the diagnosis and evaluate the effectiveness of therapy: biochemical, serological, clinical and instrumental methods. Modern bacteriological methods of culturing and identifying aerobic, microaerophilic and anaerobic microorganisms belonging to pathogenic, opportunistic and saprophytic groups. Bacteriological method for diagnosing intestinal dysbacteriosis by serial dilutions according to Epstein-Litvak (1977), with additions by N.M. Gracheva (1987), in modification. The degree of microflora disorder was determined by the

dysbacteriosis index (DI), which was calculated as the ratio of the number of facultative microorganisms to endogenous microorganisms. DI in the control group < 1.0 . Statistical processing of the results was carried out using the Fisher-Student variation statistics method. The obtained results were processed and various parameters were evaluated on a computer using a set of application programs in the Excel environment on a Pentium 4 processor, methods for evaluating “questionable options”, calculating the mean value (M), the error of the mean value (t), and the standard deviation (o). The significance of differences was determined by Student’s t-test.

Results and discussion. As a result of the first stage of the study, in order to determine the frequency of infectious complications and the nature of the microbial flora in patients with rheumatic diseases (RD), an analysis of 1054 case histories and outpatient cards of patients with RD was performed: 696 women (66%) and 358 men (34%). The average age of the patients was 44.4 ± 10.2 years, with women being slightly older - 46.8 ± 12.7 years, and men - 41.2 ± 12.3 years ($p > 0.05$). Screening analysis showed that 1/3 (27.9%) of patients with rheumatic pathology have chronic or acute infectious diseases. As expected, infections are most often defined as infection-associated RA, with the most common being reactive arthritis (RA), Reiter's disease (RD) and chronic rheumatic heart disease (CRHD). In psoriatic arthritis (PA), a lower percentage of infections was recorded. Infections in systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) accounted for 27.4%, in Bechterew's disease (BD) — 20.0%, in systemic sclerosis (SSc) — 23.3%, in rheumatoid arthritis (RA) — 20.3%, in deforming osteoarthritis (DOA) — 19.7%, in primary gout (PG) — 17.4%. The most common localization of chronic foci of infection is the genitourinary system — 57 patients — 19.3% excluding sexually transmitted infections. Pyelonephritis accounted for 51 cases (17.3%), adnexitis — 3 (1.0%), colpitis — 2 (0.7%), and cystitis — 1 (0.3%). Pyelonephritis complicates the course of all diseases, but is most often observed in RA and DOA. Respiratory tract infections were detected in 25.2% of individuals: tonsillitis - 32 (10.9%), pharyngitis - 19 (6.5%), bronchitis - 9 (3.0%), otitis - 9 (3.0%), sinusitis - 4 (1.4%), pneumonia - 1 (0.3%). In patients with PA, respiratory tract infections - tonsillitis, pharyngitis - were most common. 30 patients (10.3%) had chronic inflammatory processes in the digestive organs: cholecystitis, colitis, most often these diseases were observed in older patients. Intestinal infections accounted for 1.4% (4 patients), the etiologic agents were yersiniosis (2) and salmonellosis (2).

Viral infection was rare — in 5 patients (1.7%): herpes in 3 patients with RA and cytomegalovirus infection in 2 patients. When studying the quantitative and qualitative composition of the intestinal microflora of the examined patients, differences in the level of endogenous and facultative microflora were revealed. The greatest decrease in endogenous flora was noted in the group of patients with DOA (a decrease of 2.1 times), with BP — by 1.3 times, with RA — by 1.7 times. The level of endogenous, facultative and proteolytic microorganisms of the intestinal microflora in the amount of 1 G CFU/g increased with PP by 19.2%, and with RA — by 30.2%. In the composition of facultative microflora, the proportion of proteolytic bacteria (PB) of the intestinal group with PP increases — up to 52.6% of their total number. The share of PB in the number of the facultative group of bacteria with Ra is 31.4%. In DOA, the content of Pb was not recorded, in the group with the facultative variant it slightly decreased. The effect of anti-inflammatory drug therapy on the level of intestinal dysbacteriosis (ID) was assessed. The results of bacteriological studies of the intestinal microflora were compared in groups of patients who received NMSM therapy for 6 months - 1 year (group A), NMSM + glucocorticoids (group B) and NMSM - more than 1 year (group C). It was found that in groups B and C, profound disturbances of the microflora were noted, up to the development of ID. Statistically significant differences in

the composition of the intestinal microflora were noted in the group of patients with RA depending on the duration and regularity of drug intake. For a more convenient characterization of the intestinal microflora of the examined patients and assessment of the dynamics of changes, we used an integral indicator - the dysbacteriosis index (DI). This indicator, characterized by the ratio of facultative bacteria of the microflora to endogenous microorganisms (Table 1), was associated with arthritis activity: thus, grade III dysbiosis was more often detected in patients with high activity of RA, DOA, PP. In most patients with moderate and low activity of the process, grade II ID was observed in 50% of cases. Patients with high and moderate activity of RA were diagnosed more reliably than patients with low activity and patients with DOA and PP.

Thus, it has been established that patients with RA, DOA and PD have pronounced intestinal dysbiosis, the development and degree of which depend on the duration of NMSM therapy and the degree of arthritis activity. Dysbacteriosis in RA, DOA and PD is characterized by a deficiency of bifido- and lactoflora and an increase in the amount and spectrum of UMP. A high risk of disruption of the biotope microflora and development of infection in the intestine, as well as the development of dysbacteriosis in patients, which is the basis for biocorrection, has been revealed. We assessed the clinical and microbiological efficacy of a course of probiotics together with microbiological correction one month after the end of treatment and thereafter. We selected the following criteria for clinical and microbiological efficacy: good result - no complaints and intestinal dysbacteriosis or moderate microbiological disorders; satisfactory - the clinical effect is unstable or incomplete, the presence of intestinal dysbacteriosis after completion of treatment; unsatisfactory - no changes in the patient's condition, the presence of microbiological abnormalities. It was found that good efficiency of probiotic therapy was noted in 66.7% of treated patients. It should be noted that clinical and microbiological results of long-term (more than a month after the end of therapy) treatment are worse than in the previous one.

Conclusion. As a result of the conducted studies, it was found that in patients with RA, DOA and BP the microflora of various biotopes is disturbed. The most pronounced disturbances are observed in the intestinal microflora - up to the development of dysbacteriosis of II-III degree, which has certain characteristic features: in RA there is a decrease in endogenous flora and an increase in facultative bacteria, in DOA the amount of endogenous flora sharply decreases with an insignificant change in the facultative group of bacteria, in BP the proportion of coliform bacteria increases. Characteristics of microflora and its expression in units (units). With $ID < 1.0$, endogenous flora prevails over facultative - normoflora. Dysbacteriosis is defined as $ID > 1.0$. As can be seen in RA, DOA, PP, the dysbacteriosis index reaches high values in the acute period of the disease, decreases slightly during the remission period, but does not reach normal values. The depth of intestinal microbiocenosis disturbance in patients with chronic concomitant pathology consists in the appearance of opportunistic and pathogenic bacteria in its composition, activation of opportunistic microorganisms due to a decrease in the colonization resistance of autoflora and secondary immunodeficiency. Inclusion of Bifidumbacterium — PL and Lactobacterium probiotics in complex therapy leads to a good clinical and laboratory effect in 66.7% of treated patients, reduces the frequency and intensity of arthritis exacerbations and, accordingly, improves the quality of life of patients.

REFERENCES

1. Abdulganieva D. I., Nasonov E. I. Clinical and pathogenetic parallels of esophageal lesions in patients with rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthrosis with the first non-steroidal anti-

- inflammatory drugs. *Clinical Perspectives of Gastroenterology, Hepatology*: 2011. - N5. - P. 45-49.
2. Grinin V., Kovaleva I. Rheumatic diseases: social and hygienic aspects: Doctor: 2014. - N7. - P. 67-69
 3. Zhilin S. A., Radchenko V. G., Dobritsa V. P. *Bulletin of the North-Western State Medical University named after I. I. Mechnikov*: 2013. - N2. - P. 111-117.
 4. Kiselius V. E. Chronic tonsillitis, weakened juvenile rheumatoid arthritis: *Bulletin of Otolaryngology*: 2015. - N4. - P. 88-89.
 5. Ushkalova E. A. Modern concepts of the role of probiotics in the prevention and treatment of various diseases: focus on Linex: *Therapeutic archive*: 2014. - N4. - P. 117-124.
 6. Formation of biofilms by opportunistic microorganisms isolated from patients with rheumatic diseases. Malafeeva E. V., Gulneva M. Yu., Noskov S. M., Romanov V. A.: *Clinical and laboratory diagnostics*: 2014. - No. - P. 53-55.
 7. Chronic joint diseases: Chichasova N. B. Imameddinova G. R. Igolkina E. B. Nasonov E. L.: Doctor: 2013. - N5. - P. 84-91.
 8. Chichasova N. B. Imameddinova G. R. Modern treatment of rheumatoid arthritis: recommendations and real practice: *Farmateka*: 2014. - N19. - P. 36-42.
 9. Enteropathic spondylitis: from diagnosis to treatment. Peluso R. L., Di Minno M. N., Lervolino S., Manguso F., Tramontano G., Ambrosino P., Esposito S., Scalera A., Castiglione F., Scarpa R. *Clin Dev Immunol*. 2013; 2013: 631408. DOI: 10.1155/2013/631408. Epub 2013 Apr 15.
 10. Newman MG, Nanau RM. Inflammatory bowel disease: role of diet, microbiota, and lifestyle. *Translational Research*. 2012;160(1):29-44.
 11. Veerappan GR, Betteridge J, Young PE. Probiotics for the treatment of inflammatory bowel disease. *Current Gastroenterology Reports*. 2012;14(4):324-333.